

Sonocatalytic rapid degradation of organic dye pollutants on the novel zeolite Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄ ternary nanocomposite from water media

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Abstract

This research focuses mainly on the sonocatalytic degradation of organic dye pollutants using the zeolite Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄ ternary nanocomposite from water media. For this purpose, initially, Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄ nanocomposite was successfully synthesized by the ultrasonic-assisted solvothermal method. The morphology, structure, magnetic and functional groups identifications of the as-synthesized catalysts were studied via FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD, and VSM analyses. The sonocatalytic activity of Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄ was then evaluated in the organic dyes degradation, including congo red (CR), methylene blue (MB), rhodamine B (RhB), and malachite green (MG). To investigate the sonocatalytic performance of the Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄, the main key parameters like irradiation time, initial dye concentration, catalyst dosage, H₂O₂ concentration, and organic dye type were surveyed. The maximum sonocatalytic yields of 100%, 99.5% 97.1% and 95.3% were gained for CR, MG, MB, and RhB on the Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄ in the presence of the ultrasonic (US)/H₂O₂ system, respectively. Furthermore, •OH radicals as the main reactive oxygen species throughout the sonodegradation reaction were identified. Additionally, the as-synthesized Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄ nanocomposite illustrated noteworthy stability and reproducibility for four sequential sonocatalyst runs.

Keywords: Y/MIL-100(Fe)/MgFe₂O₄, nanocomposite, catalyst, organic dyes, sonodegradation.